

SOME Q -FEJÉR INEQUALITIES FOR $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -CONVEX FUNCTIONS

Nguyen Ngoc Hue¹

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we consider a class of generalized convex functions, which are defined according to a pair of quasi-arithmetic means and called $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex functions and establish some q -Fejér inequalities for such a function class.

Keywords: Convex function, Hermite-Hadamard inequality, Fejér inequality, q -integral inequality, q -calculus.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Hermite-Hadamard inequality was first introduced in 1883 by Hermite (Hermite, 1883) and 10 years later by Hadamard (Hadamard, 1893): Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a convex function, then

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \leq \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2}. \quad (1)$$

The weighted form of the Hermite-Hadamard inequality was given by Fejér (Fejér, 1996): If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a convex function, $g : [a, b] \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is an integrable function with $\int_a^b g(x) dx > 0$ and symmetry to $\frac{a+b}{2}$, i.e., $g(x) = g(a+b-x)$ for all $x \in [a, b]$, then

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{\int_a^b f(x)g(x) dx}{\int_a^b g(x) dx} \leq \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2}. \quad (2)$$

The concept of q -calculus was introduced by Jackson in 1910 (Jackson, 1910), then widely applied in other fields such as number theory, combinatorics, hypergeometric functions, orthogonal polynomials, quantum theory, mechanics and is considered a bridge between mathematics and physics (see Ernst, 2012, Kac & Cheung, 2022). In articles Tariboon & Ntouyas, 2013, 2014, the concept of q -derivative and q -integral on a finite $[a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}$ and established a number of versions of integral inequalities for the concept of q -integral.

Alp and co-authors (Alp & et al., 2018) established the q -Hermite-Hadamard inequality for left q -integrals: If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a convex function, then

$$f\left(\frac{qa+b}{1+q}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) d_q x \leq \frac{qf(a)+f(b)}{1+q}. \quad (3)$$

Bermudo and colleagues in 2020 introduced the concept of right q -integral and established the q -Hermite-Hadamard inequality for convex

functions $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as follows

$$f\left(\frac{a+qb}{1+q}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) d_q x \leq \frac{f(a)+qf(b)}{1+q}. \quad (4)$$

Inequalities (3) and (4) have recently received extensive research attention, see for example works Liu & Hefeng, 2016, Noor & et al., 2015.

Most recently, Ali and co-authors in 2023 proposed another version of the q -Hermite-Hadamard inequality involving left q -integral and right q -integral as follows: If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a convex function, then

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \left[\int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f(x) d_q x + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b f(x) d_q x \right] \leq \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2}. \quad (5)$$

Inspired by the studies mentioned above, in this paper, we establish some q -Fejér type inequalities for the class of $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex functions. Our results are extensions and refinements of recent results for the q -Hermite-Hadamard inequality.

2. RESEARCH CONTENTS AND METHODS

2.1. Research contents

- $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex function.
- The q -Fejér inequality for the class of $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex functions.

2.2. Research methods

- Theoretical mathematical research includes analysis, comparison, contrast, generalization, and specialization to predict and introduce new inequalities;
- Using estimates and assessments based on convex function theory;
- Incorporates several new methods and

¹Faculty of Natural Science and Technology, Tay Nguyen University;
Corresponding author: Nguyen Ngoc Hue; Tel: 0905684768, Email: nnhue@ttn.edu.vn.

techniques recently developed by us when constructing Fejér-type inequalities for $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex functions.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

First, we recall the definition of a $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex function and its basic properties. In this article, symbols I and J are real number intervals, $\phi: I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\psi: J \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are strictly monotone and continuous functions. Use the pair of quasi-arithmetic mean \mathcal{M}_ϕ and \mathcal{M}_ψ , where

$$\mathcal{M}_\psi(a, b; \alpha) = \phi^{-1}(\alpha\phi(a) + (1-\alpha)\phi(b))$$

Aumann (Aumann, 1933) introduced the concept of $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex function as follows.

Definition 1 (Aumann, 1933). $f: I \rightarrow J$ is called $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex function if

$$f(\mathcal{M}(a, b; \alpha)) \leq \mathcal{M}_\psi(f(a), f(b); \alpha) \quad (6)$$

for all $a, b \in I$ and $\alpha \in [0; 1]$.

In the case where inequality (6) is satisfied with $\phi(x) = x$, we say f is \mathcal{M}_ψ -convex, and if f satisfies inequality (6) with $\phi(x) = x$ and $\psi(x)$, then f is a convex function.

Note, if ψ is an increasing function then $f: I \rightarrow J$ is $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex if and only if $\psi \circ f \circ \phi^{-1}$ is convex on $\phi(I)$. And if ψ is a decreasing function, then $f: I \rightarrow J$ is $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex if and only if $\psi \circ f \circ \phi^{-1}$ is a concave function on $\phi(I)$.

Lemma 2. (Niculescu & Persson, 2006, Lemma A.22) If ψ is increasing on J , then $f: I \rightarrow J$ is $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex function if and only if $g(x) = \psi \circ f \circ \phi^{-1}(x)$ is convex on $\phi(I)$.

Next is some knowledge about q -derivatives and q -integrals where q is always understood as a real number in the range $(0, 1)$.

Definition 3. (Tariboon & Ntouyas, 2013) Let $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a continuous function. Then q -the left derivative of f at $x \in [a, b]$ is defined as follows

$${}_a D_q f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{f(x) - f(qx + (1-q)a)}{(1-q)(x-a)}, & x \neq a \\ \lim_{x \rightarrow a} {}_a D_q f(x) & , x = a \end{cases}$$

A function f is called q -differentiable on $[a, b]$ if ${}_a D_q f(x)$ exists for all $x \in [a, b]$.

Definition 4. (Tariboon & Ntouyas, 2013) Let $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a continuous function. Then q -left integral of f at $x \in [a, b]$ is defined as follows

$$\int_a^x f(t) {}_a d_q(t) = (1-q)(x-a) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^n f(q^n x + (1-q^n)a).$$

A function f is called q -integrable on $[a, b]$ if

$$\int_a^x f(x) {}_a d_q(t) \text{ exists for all } x \in [a, b].$$

In particular, if $a = 0$ then we get the Jackson q -integral (Jackson, 1910)

$$\int_0^x f(t) {}_0 d_q(t) = \int_0^x f(t) d_q(t) = (1-q)x \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^n f(q^n x).$$

Comment 5. (Bermudo & et al., 2020, Tariboon & Ntouyas, 2013, 2014) Let $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a continuous function, then

$$1. {}_a D_q \int_a^x f(x) {}_a d_q(t) = f(x) - f(a).$$

$$2. \int_a^x {}_a D_q f(x) {}_a d_q(t) = f(x) - f(c) \text{ for all } c \in (a, x).$$

$$3. \int_a^x [\alpha f(x) + \beta g(x)] {}_a d_q(t) = \alpha \int_a^x f(x) {}_a d_q(t) + \beta \int_a^x g(x) {}_a d_q(t).$$

4. If g is a continuous function on $[a, b]$ and $f(t) \leq g(t)$ for all $t \in [a, b]$ then

$$\int_a^x f(t) {}_a d_q(t) \leq \int_a^x g(t) {}_a d_q(t).$$

On the other hand, Bermudo and colleagues in 2020 introduced the concepts of right q -derivative and right q -integral as follows.

Definition 6. (Bermudo & et al., 2020) Let $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a continuous function. Then, q -the left derivative of f at $x \in [a, b]$ is defined as follows

$${}_b D_q f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{f(qx + (1-q)b) - f(x)}{(1-q)(b-x)}, & x \neq b \\ \lim_{x \rightarrow b} {}_b D_q f(x) & , x = b \end{cases}$$

A function f is called q -differentiable on $[a, b]$ if ${}_b D_q f(x)$ exists for all $x \in [a, b]$.

Definition 7. (Bermudo & et al., 2020) Let $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a continuous function. Then q -right integral of f at $x \in [a, b]$ is defined as follows

$$\int_x^b f(t) {}_b d_q(t) = (1-q)(b-x) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^n f(q^n x + (1-q^n)b)$$

A function f is called q -integrable right on $[a, b]$

if $\int_x^b f(x) {}_b d_q(t)$ exists for all $x \in [a, b]$.

From Remark 5, we can also obtain similar properties for the right q -integral.

Next, we will establish and prove the q -Hermite-Hadamard inequality and the q -Fejér inequality for the $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex function.

In this article, we always assume $f: I \rightarrow J$ is a $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex function; $a, b \in I$ with $a < b$; $\alpha \in (0; 1)$; $q \in (0; 1)$; $w: [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, \infty)$

is a q -integral function and satisfies the condition $\int_0^1 w(t) d_q t > 0$ for all $s \in (\bar{u}]$. Symbol

$$\mathcal{L}(t) = \mathcal{M}_\phi(a, \mathcal{M}_\phi(a, b; \alpha); t)$$

and

$$\mathcal{R}(t) = \mathcal{M}_\phi(b, \mathcal{M}_\phi(a, b; \alpha); t)$$

with $t \in [0, 1]$.

Lemma 8. (Duc & et al., 2020) Let $\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G}: [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be functions respectively defined by

$$\mathcal{F}(t) = \mathcal{M}_\psi(f \circ \mathcal{L}(t), f \circ \mathcal{R}(t); \alpha)$$

and

$$\mathcal{G}(t) = \mathcal{M}_\psi(\mathcal{F}(1), \mathcal{F}(0); t).$$

Then, \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are \mathcal{M}_ψ -convex, increasing functions on $[0, 1]$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}(0) &= \mathcal{G}(0) = f(\mathcal{M}_\phi(a, b; \alpha)) \\ \mathcal{F}(t) &\leq \mathcal{G}(t), \quad t \in [0, 1], \\ \mathcal{F}(1) &= \mathcal{G}(1) = \mathcal{M}_\phi(f(a), f(b); \alpha). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Theorem 9 (q -Hermite-Hadamard inequality). Let $f: I \rightarrow J$ be a $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex function. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &f(\mathcal{M}_\phi(a, b; \alpha)) \\ &\leq \frac{(1-\alpha)}{\phi(b) - \phi(a)} \int_a^{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a, b; \alpha)} \psi \circ f(x)_a d_q \phi(x) \\ &+ \frac{\alpha}{\phi(b) - \phi(a)} \int_{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a, b; \alpha)}^b \psi \circ f(x)_b d_q \phi(x) \quad (8) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{1+q} \psi(\mathcal{M}_\phi(f(a), f(b); \alpha)) \\ &+ \frac{q}{1+q} \psi \circ f(\mathcal{M}_\phi(a, b; \alpha)). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. For all $t \in [0, 1]$

$$\begin{aligned} \psi \circ \mathcal{F}(0) &\leq \psi \circ \mathcal{F}(t) = \alpha \psi \circ f \circ \phi^{-1}(A(t)) \\ &+ (1-\alpha) \psi \circ f \circ \phi^{-1}(B(t)) \quad (9) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$A(t) = t\phi(a) + (1-t)(\alpha\phi(a) + (1-\alpha)\phi(b))$$

and

$$B(t) = t\phi(b) + (1-t)(\alpha\phi(a) + (1-\alpha)\phi(b)).$$

Taking q -integrate both sides of (9) we get $\psi \circ f(\mathcal{M}_\phi(a, b; \alpha)) \leq \alpha \int_0^1 \psi \circ f \circ \phi^{-1}(A(t)) d_q t$

$$\begin{aligned} &+ (1-\alpha) \int_0^1 \psi \circ f \circ \phi^{-1}(B(t)) d_q t \\ &= \frac{(1-\alpha)}{\phi(b) - \phi(a)} \int_a^{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a, b; \alpha)} \psi \circ f(x)_a d_q \phi(x) \\ &+ \frac{\alpha}{\phi(b) - \phi(a)} \int_{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a, b; \alpha)}^b \psi \circ f(x)_b d_q \phi(x). \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand

$$\begin{aligned} \psi \circ \mathcal{F}(t) &\leq t\psi(\mathcal{M}_\phi(f(a), f(b); \alpha)) \\ &+ (1-t)\psi \circ f(\mathcal{M}_\phi(a, b; \alpha)). \end{aligned}$$

Taking q -integrate both sides we get

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^1 \psi \circ \mathcal{F}(t) d_q t &\leq \psi(\mathcal{M}_\phi(f(a), f(b); \alpha)) \int_0^1 t d_q t \\ &+ \psi \circ f(\mathcal{M}_\phi(a, b; \alpha)) \int_0^1 (1-t) d_q t \\ &= \frac{1}{1+q} \psi(\mathcal{M}_\phi(f(a), f(b); \alpha)) \\ &+ \frac{q}{1+q} \psi \circ f(\mathcal{M}_\phi(a, b; \alpha)). \end{aligned}$$

The theorem has been proven.

Comment 10. In case f is a convex function $\psi(x) = \phi(x) = x$, inequality (8) becomes q -Hermite-Hadamard inequality (5). By choosing special functions ψ and ϕ , we will get q -Hermite-Hadamard inequalities for generalized convex functions such as log-convex function, harmonic convex function, kernel convex function, harmonic log-convex function, p -convex function,...

Theorem 11. With $s \in (0, 1]$, we set

$$\mathcal{L}(s) = \psi^{-1} \left(\frac{\int_0^s \psi \circ \mathcal{F}(t) w(t) d_q t}{\int_0^s w(t) d_q t} \right)$$

and

$$\beta(s) = \frac{\int_0^s t w(t) d_q t}{\int_0^s w(t) d_q t}.$$

Then $\mathcal{F} \circ \beta$, \mathcal{L} and $\mathcal{G} \circ \beta$ are increasing functions on $(0, 1]$ and satisfied

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0^+} \mathcal{F} \circ \beta(s) = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0^+} \mathcal{L}(s) = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0^+} \mathcal{G} \circ \beta(s) = \mathcal{G}(0),$$

$$\mathcal{F} \circ \beta(s) \leq \mathcal{L}(s) \leq \mathcal{G} \circ \beta(s), \quad s \in (0, 1]. \quad (10)$$

To prove the above theorem, we need the following result.

Lemma 12. Let $P: [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a increasing, continuous function. With $s \in (0, 1]$, we set

$$P_1(s) = \frac{\int_0^s P(t) w(t) d_q t}{\int_0^s w(t) d_q t}.$$

Then P_1 is a increasing function on $(0, 1]$ and

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0^+} P_1(s) = P(0) \leq P_1(s) \leq P(s), \quad s \in (0, 1]. \quad (11)$$

Proof. Proof similar to Duc & et al. 2020 Lemma 2.4.

Now we prove Theorem 11.

Proof Theorem 11. Since ψ is strictly monotonic, we need to consider two cases of ψ .

Suppose first that ψ increases strictly on J . Since ψ is continuous on J , ψ^{-1} is continuous and strictly increasing on $\psi(J)$.

Applying Lemma 8 and Lemma 12 to $P = \psi \circ \mathcal{F}$, $\psi \circ \mathcal{L}$ increases on $(0,1]$ with

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0^+} \psi \circ \mathcal{L}(s) = \psi \circ \mathcal{F}(0).$$

Since ψ^{-1} is continuous and strictly increasing on $\psi(J)$, \mathcal{L} increases on $(0,1]$ and

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0^+} \mathcal{L}(s) = \psi \circ \mathcal{F}(0).$$

Again according to Lemma 12, we have β increasing on $(0,1]$ with

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0^+} \beta(s) = 0 \leq \beta(s) \leq s, \quad s \in (0,1].$$

Therefore $\mathcal{F} \circ \beta$ and $\mathcal{G} \circ \beta$ determine, increase on $(0,1]$ and

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0^+} \mathcal{F} \circ \beta(s) = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0^+} \mathcal{G} \circ \beta(s) = \mathcal{G}(0).$$

Next, we prove the inequalities in (10). Fixed $s \in (0,1]$. Applying Jensen's inequality (see Pečarić & et al., 1992, Chapter 2) to the convex function $\psi \circ \mathcal{F}$ on the interval $[0, s]$, we get

Because $\mathcal{F}(t) \leq \mathcal{G}(t)$, so

$$\psi \circ \mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\int_0^s t w(t) d_q t}{\int_0^s w(t) d_q t} \right) \leq \frac{\int_0^s \psi \circ \mathcal{F}(t) w(t) d_q t}{\int_0^s w(t) d_q t}.$$

Inferred that

$$\mathcal{F} \circ \beta(s) \leq \mathcal{L}(s).$$

Due to $\mathcal{F}(t) \leq \mathcal{G}(t)$, $t \in [\ddot{u}]$, the continuity of the functions $\mathcal{F}(t)$ and $\mathcal{G}(t)$ on $[0,1]$ along with the monotonicity of the q -integral, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\int_0^s \psi \circ \mathcal{F}(t) w(t) d_q t}{\int_0^s w(t) d_q t} &\leq \frac{\int_0^s \psi \circ \mathcal{G}(t) w(t) d_q t}{\int_0^s w(t) d_q t} \\ &= \psi \circ \mathcal{G} \circ \beta(s). \end{aligned}$$

Because ψ^{-1} increases

$$\mathcal{L}(s) \leq \mathcal{G} \circ \beta(s).$$

The theorem is proven similarly for the case where ψ is a decreasing function.

From Theorem 11, we can establish a number of Fejér-type inequalities for $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex functions by choosing different w functions. For example, we choose

$$w(t) = (1-\alpha)g \circ \mathcal{L}(t) + \alpha g \circ \mathcal{R}(t), \quad t \in [0,1],$$

where $g : [a,b] \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is chosen satisfactorily

$$\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha} g \circ \mathcal{L}(t) = \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} g \circ \mathcal{R}(t), \quad t \in [0, s] \quad (12)$$

Note that when $\alpha = 1/2$ and $\phi(x) = x$, Assumption (12) reduces to the assumption that g is symmetric about $(a+b)/2$.

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^s w(t) d_q t &= (1-\alpha) \int_0^s g \circ \mathcal{L}(t) d_q t + \alpha \int_0^s g \circ \mathcal{R}(t) d_q t \\ &= \frac{1}{\phi(b) - \phi(a)} \int_{\mathcal{L}(s)}^{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a,b;\alpha)} g(x)_a d_q \phi(x) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\phi(b) - \phi(a)} \int_{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a,b;\alpha)}^{\mathcal{R}(s)} g(x)^b d_q \phi(x) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^s \psi \circ \mathcal{F}(t) w(t) d_q t &= (1-\alpha) \int_0^s (\psi \circ f \circ \mathcal{L}(t)) g \circ \mathcal{L}(t) d_q t \\ &\quad + \alpha \int_0^s (\psi \circ f \circ \mathcal{R}(t)) g \circ \mathcal{R}(t) d_q t \\ &= \frac{1}{\phi(b) - \phi(a)} \int_{\mathcal{L}(s)}^{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a,b;\alpha)} (\psi \circ f(x)) g(x)_a d_q \phi(x) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\phi(b) - \phi(a)} \int_{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a,b;\alpha)}^{\mathcal{R}(s)} (\psi \circ f(x)) g(x)^b d_q \phi(x) \end{aligned}$$

And so

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(s) &= \psi^{-1} \left[\frac{\int_{\mathcal{L}(s)}^{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a,b;\alpha)} (\psi \circ f(x)) g(x)_a d_q \phi(x)}{\int_{\mathcal{L}(s)}^{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a,b;\alpha)} g(x)_a d_q \phi(x) + \int_{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a,b;\alpha)}^{\mathcal{R}(s)} g(x)^b d_q \phi(x)} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\int_{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a,b;\alpha)}^{\mathcal{R}(s)} (\psi \circ f(x)) g(x)^b d_q \phi(x)}{\int_{\mathcal{L}(s)}^{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a,b;\alpha)} g(x)_a d_q \phi(x) + \int_{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a,b;\alpha)}^{\mathcal{R}(s)} g(x)^b d_q \phi(x)} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Together with Theorem 11, we have the following result.

Corollary 13 (q -Fejér inequality). *Let $f : I \rightarrow J$ be a $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex function. Suppose $g : [a,b] \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a q -integral function, with*

$$\int_0^s g \circ \mathcal{L}(t) d_q t > 0$$

for all $s \in (0,1]$ and satisfy (12). Then, for all $s \in (0,1]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &f(\mathcal{M}_\phi(a,b;\alpha)) \\ &\leq \mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\int_0^s t g_1 \circ \mathcal{L}(t) d_q t}{\int_0^s g_1 \circ \mathcal{L}(t) d_q t} \right) \\ &\leq \psi^{-1} \left[\frac{\int_{\mathcal{L}(s)}^{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a,b;\alpha)} (\psi \circ f(x)) g(x)_a d_q \phi(x)}{\int_{\mathcal{L}(s)}^{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a,b;\alpha)} g(x)_a d_q \phi(x) + \int_{\mathcal{M}_\phi(a,b;\alpha)}^{\mathcal{R}(s)} g(x)^b d_q \phi(x)} \right. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left. + \frac{\int_{\mathcal{M}_\psi(a,b;\alpha)}^{\mathcal{R}(s)} (\psi \circ f(x))g(x)^b d_q \phi(x)}{\int_{\mathcal{L}(s)}^{\mathcal{M}_\psi(a,b;\alpha)} g(x)_a d_q \phi(x) + \int_{\mathcal{M}_\psi(a,b;\alpha)}^{\mathcal{R}(s)} g(x)^b d_q \phi(x)} \right] \\
 & \leq \mathcal{G} \left(\frac{\int_0^s t g \circ \mathcal{L}(t) d_q t}{\int_0^s g \circ \mathcal{L}(t) d_q t} \right) \\
 & \leq \psi^{-1}(\alpha \psi \circ f(a) + (1-\alpha)\psi \circ f(b)). \quad (13)
 \end{aligned}$$

Comment 14.

1. In (13), if given $p \rightarrow 1$ then we get the Fejér inequality for the $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex function established in Duc & et al., 2020.

2. By choosing special functions ψ and ϕ , we will get q -Fejér inequalities for generalized convex functions, such as log-convex function, harmonic convex function, kernel convex function, harmonic log-convex function, p -convex function.

3. In addition, inequality (13) is also an extension and smoothing of inequalities (5), (8). Indeed, choose $\alpha = 1/2$, $g = 1$ and $\psi(x) = \phi(x) = x$. Then, inequality (13) follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 & f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \\
 & \leq \frac{f\left(\frac{(2q+3)a+(2q+1)b}{4(1+q)}\right) + f\left(\frac{(2q+1)a+(2q+3)b}{4(1+q)}\right)}{2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \leq \frac{2}{b-a} \left[\int_{\frac{(q+2)a+b}{2(1+q)}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f(x)_a d_q x + \int_{\frac{a+(q+2)b}{2}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f(x)^b d_q x \right] \\
 & \leq \frac{f\left(\frac{(q+2)a+b}{2(1+q)}\right) + f\left(\frac{a+(q+2)b}{2(1+q)}\right)}{2} \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \left[\int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f(x)_a d_q x + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b f(x)^b d_q x \right] \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{1+q} \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} + \frac{q}{1+q} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \\
 & \leq \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2}.
 \end{aligned}$$

4. CONCLUSION

In the article, we have established and proven the q -Hermite-Hadamard inequality and q -Fejér inequality for the class of $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -convex functions. The new inequalities are extended, smoothed results for the q -Hermite-Hadamard inequality for the class of convex functions. The new techniques in estimation and evaluation used in the article can be applied for further research in the field of q -integral inequalities related to other classes of generalized convex functions.

MỘT SỐ BẤT ĐẲNG THỨC Q-FEJÉR CHO HÀM $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -LÒI

Nguyễn Ngọc Huệ¹

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TÓM TẮT

Trong bài báo này, chúng tôi xem xét một lớp hàm lồi mở rộng liên quan đến một cặp tựa trung bình số học, được gọi là hàm $(\mathcal{M}_\phi, \mathcal{M}_\psi)$ -lồi từ đó thiết lập một số bất đẳng thức q -Fejér cho lớp hàm lồi này.

Từ khóa: Hàm lồi, Bất đẳng thức Hemiter-Hadamard, Bất đẳng thức Fejér, Bất đẳng thức q -tích phân, q -giải tích

¹Khoa Khoa học Tự nhiên và Công nghệ, Trường Đại học Tây Nguyên;
 Tác giả liên hệ: Nguyễn Ngọc Huệ; ĐT: 0905684768; Email: nnhue@ttn.edu.vn.

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